

EASY WAYS OF LEARNING ENGLISH IRREGULAR VERBS

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Annotation: This paper provides examples of learning the two forms of the past simple tense through literature that expose pragmatic learning outcomes without the need of grammatical rules during the early to mid-learning stages. Simultaneously, the learners get to learn the English culture, which broadens their perceptions of the language since culture and language are intertwined with one another. In addition, the learners would have the opportunity to appreciate the culture and civilization of the target language. To determine how these outcomes can be implemented in classrooms, this paper manifests a new emergence of understanding literature by emphasizing on innovating challenging and enthusiastic teaching methodologies to extrinsically motivate today's learners. Examples of the use of literature for teaching grammar in a class are provided throughout the research.

Keywords: approach, language acquisition, memorization, vocabulary, Enthusiasm, knowledge, desire, inquisitiveness.

When you finally think that you understand English grammar and all the different tenses, then you discover irregular verbs.

Regular verbs always follow the same pattern in the past form. They look the same in the past tense and are easy to form any time. Usually all you have to do is to add the letters *-ed* at the end of the word (wanted, played, laughed, etc.)¹

Irregular verbs do not follow that rule. You may recognize them because they look so different in the past tense (gave, sat, thought, went, etc.) But do not worry about that! This guide will help you learn to identify English irregular verbs and how to remember them easily.²

1. Memorize the 35 most common irregular verb list first³

To go a bit deeper, in English verb is irregular **when it does not end in -ed** in the **simple past tense form** and **past participle form**. Here is a simple way of looking at it:

The **simple past tense** describes any action that takes place before right now, that shows past.

- ✓ **Regular verb:** I *prepared* about 40 letters last week.
- ✓ **Irregular verb:** I *spoke* to my bestie yesterday.

The **past participle** is used in other English tenses that have an auxiliary (or “helping”) verb. For example, the past perfect tense uses the auxiliary verb “have” + the past participle of your main verb to describe an action that happened *and* ended in the past.

¹ Shahrukh -Mirzo Rahmanov; Iskandar Sattibayev. a guide to quick memorization of English words. "Istiqlol Nuri" publishing house, Tashkent, 2015.

² <https://www.wikihow.com/Learn-English-Irregular-Verbs>

³ <https://www.worddy.co/en/list-of-irregular-verbs-english>

- ✓ **Regular verb:** *I had worked* for the company for only 5 months when I decided to leave.
- ✓ **Irregular verb:** *I had spoken* at over 10 schools by the time I turned 30.

Not all irregular verbs are commonly used all the time. You may never use a word like *broadcast*, and you will probably only see the word *abide* as part of the phrase *law-abiding citizen* (that is someone who follows the law).

Instead of going through the list in alphabetical order, focus on the most commonly used word list first. Start with these very common verbs:⁴

Infinitive	Past	Past Participle
be	was	been
say	said	said
go	went	gone
come	came	come
know	knew	known
get	got	gotten
give	gave	given
become	became	become
find	found	found
think	thought	thought
see	saw	seen
drink	drank	drunk
eat	ate	eaten
write	wrote	written
sleep	slept	slept
teach	taught	taught
run	ran	run
sit	sat	sat
take	took	taken
understand	understood	understood
fly	flew	flown
throw	threw	thrown
speak	spoke	spoken
pay	paid	paid
win	won	won
wear	wore	worn
begin	began	begun
drive	drove	driven
spend	spent	spent
feel	felt	felt
swim	swam	swum
buy	bought	bought
make	made	made

⁴ Martin H. Manser. 2008. Oxford Learner’s Pocket Dictionary. (4th ed) New York: Oxford University Press.

sell	sold	sold
find	found	found

That is right, all these are tiny but very important verbs are irregular! You will need to know their irregular forms to use them in daily life.

2. Learn all new vocabularies with their tense forms⁵

You can make irregular verbs easier for yourself in the future by the way of learning them right from the beginning. Every moment you learn a new verb, learn its tenses as well.

Do not just learn that *to steal* means to take something without permission, you should also learn that its simple past tense is *stole* and its past participle form is *stolen*.

3. Turn memorizing irregular verb forms into a game⁶

You may have no problem remembering the irregular verbs using flashcards, but if you are having trouble why not turn it into a game?

There are a few games online that can make remembering the verbs fun and easy at the same time. The British Council has a *quiz-like game*, the MacMillan Dictionary has a *verb wheel*, and Quia has a game *similar to Jeopardy* and so on.

You can even make your own game with index cards: write the verb and their past or past participle forms (or both) on separate index cards. Then turn all the cards over in front of you with their backs up one by one.

Now you can play a memory game without any difficulties. Turn a card over, then another one. If the two cards match, you should leave them face up. If they do not, turn them back over and try again and again.

4. Group common irregular verbs together correctly

Irregular verbs do not follow any rules, which makes them so hard to remember. However some irregular verbs follow a similar *pattern*. Instead of learning the verbs in alphabetical order, you should try putting them in similar groups.

How you group the verbs depends on whatever is easiest for you, but here are a few suggestions for you:

- Verbs that remain the same in the present, past and past participle form.
✚ Examples: *put* and *set*.
- Verbs that are the same in the past forms, but not the present ones.
✚ Example: *breed, bred* and *shoot, shot*.
- Verbs that end in *-en* in the past participle form.
✚ Examples: *speak, spoken* and *wake, woken*.

5. Learn irregular verb forms in sentences⁷

It can be easier to remember the words when they are part of a sentence of a phrase. Learn words by putting them into sentences, and you will also be learning how to use them correctly.

⁵ Harmer, Jeremy. *How to Teach English*. England: Pearsonlongman.

⁶ Aldaria, Dina. 2004, *Through Drill Technique at SMA Negeri 3 Bandar Lampung*. Unpublished Theses for Sarjana Degree, Faculty of Teacher Training and Education, University Lampung.

⁷ Paramita. 2017. —*The Use of Matching Game to Improve Students' Understanding On Irregular Verb Of Simple Past Tense at the 8th Grade of Mts Al Ittihad Semowo, Pabelan 2015/2016*. Thesis. State Institute of Islamic Studies Salatiga

For the purpose of learning the word *see*, for example, you can use sentences like this: "I *see* the bee, I *saw* the snow, but I have never *seen* a bee in the snow!"

Be creative—the weirder the sentences are, the easier they will be to remember them. You are able to use rhymes, keep the sentences short or create an entire story using as many verbs as you can. How you do it is up to you, as long as it helps you remember the verbs.

6. Learn irregular verbs with songs and videos⁸

Another wonderful way to give the words more meaning is through using music. You can find many songs for remembering irregular verbs on YouTube and things like that. Here are three of the best ones:

- ❖ [FluencyMC](#) uses a catchy rap song to teach the forms of some of the most common irregular verbs correctly.
- ❖ This [adorable cat video](#) tells a story while teaching the verb forms.
- ❖ [Schoolhouse Rock](#) is a classic cartoon with fantastic music you will be singing for days after hearing it.

Music videos (and videos in general) are helpful for learning these verbs because you can hear and see each word in context. If you enjoy learning English words from videos and music, then you can search for music videos online on places like YouTube and you can make your own study playlist.

There is also the language learning program called [FluentU](#). It teaches English with authentic media like music videos and news clips as well.⁹

The videos on FluentU are sorted by topic and difficulty at the same time. They all have interactive subtitles that let you look up words as you watch and provide both translations and example sentences together.

This helps you get comfortable with irregular English verbs because you will see how they are used in native English speech as well as in a variety of situations.

7. Leave lists where you might see them

Usually just memorizing is the best way to go. To make this easier for you, divide up the verbs in groups of 5 to 10 words (you may group them alphabetically, by how common they are).

Write the verbs out on paper, and leave them in spots where you might see them throughout the day. Tape the irregular verb list up behind your coffee maker, on your table, or even on the bathroom wall! Looking at the list just a few minutes a day can be enough to remember them exactly.

Once you feel that you have remembered the full list, then move on to the next group of verbs.

8. Ask people to correct you when you make mistakes¹⁰

⁸ Seaton, Anne and Mew, Y.H. 2007. Basic English Grammar of English Language Learners. Irvine Saddleback Education Publishing.

⁹ Slaterry, W and Willis, Jane. 2003. Teaching for Foreign Language. New York: Oxford University Press.

¹⁰ Wright, A. B, David and Michael, B. 2006. Games For Language Learning. New

Nothing beats practicing—but practicing correctly is exactly important too! Whenever you are speaking to an English speaker, ask them to correct you if you make a mistake when you speak in English language. This is great way not just for irregular verbs, but for your English speaking in general.

In order to gain knowledge, first of all, the desire ought to be courage, and it is necessary to be able to use different methods. To learn a new language, we can find the right way to the highest heights in every field of our life and find our own way. It is a thankless help that invites us to take over and over. That is why, let's raise our children to be knowledgeable, enlightened mature people from a young age.

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